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DOUBLE STANDARDS AND VALUE EDUCATION

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We all as proud nations are proud of our individual rich cultural heritage, but today all around the globe we are forgetting those ideals, values, principles which were so dear to our ancestors.

The many ills that our society is suffering today are mainly due to value crisis. Hardly any day goes without some news indicating crisis of values. Erosion of social, moral, cultural, economic, political values has led to the spread of selfishness, unlimited greed, corruption, violence, and destruction, abuse of human rights, frustration and corrosion of character.

Mahatma Gandhi, the great philosopher, had mentioned 7 deadly sins pertaining to degradation of values:

- * Wealth without work
- * Pleasure without consciousness
- * Knowledge without consciousness
- * Commerce without morality
- * Science without humanity
- * Religion without sacrifice
- * Politics without principles

Today all this is evident everywhere. We have wealth, pleasure, knowledge, commerce, science, religion and politics but sans consciousness, morality, humanity and principles. Wealth is worshipped as God, pride has taken a front seat, selfishness is entrenched in intellect,

compassion has dried up, gratitude has faded away, love and affection have become full of lust and hypocrisy has become the hall mark of life. Hypocrisy or double standards have shaken the very pillars of faith, justice and equality. A double standard may take the form of an instance in which certain concepts are perceived as acceptable to be applied by one group of people but are unaccepted – rather as a taboo – when applied by another group. For example different moral standards are applicable to men and women in society. Infact double standards are present everywhere – politics, workplace, home, relations. Politicians sometimes bend their principles to suit their needs or rich people usually get away with a theft and the poor people are caught. It is ok to lie and cheat if you can get something good out of a relation. Old habits are hard to die and with double standards in morality, it is more than a habit. It is deeply rooted to the very core of society.

Why do people have double standards?

- * People find excuses for themselves : People have a tendency to defend themselves for doing a certain thing. If they insult a person it is right, but if another person does the same it is wrong.
- * Their emotions affect the way they judge others : If a person likes someone, he would probably ignore his mistakes. On the contrary he would highlight mistakes committed by someone he doesn't admire.
- * People lie to themselves : Sometimes people manipulate facts just to suit their needs. If they dislike a person, they would do whatever they like to start judging him accordingly. They would twist facts, even if that meant telling a lie, to support their beliefs.
- * Physical attractiveness and double standards : People who are attractive are treated differently than those people who are comparatively simple looking.
- * Most people want to be right : The desire to be right is very powerful. People argue even when they know they are wrong. If they dislike someone they would argue, judging him differently, just to prove they were right.

These double standard people spread filth wherever they go. They judge others more strongly on their 'morals', than do they do themselves on their 'values'. Little do people realize

that they have no right to criticize others without checking on themselves if they are right or wrong. Hypocrisy can infect the very core of human values and degrade them. So something needs to be done to combat this vice.

Here comes the role of value education. No doubt the role of education in developing values and fighting the vices can never be undermined, but values should not be divorced from cognitive development. Through a well-framed and well-planned curriculum and activities, there is need to develop intellectual virtues among students. These intellectual virtues include intellectual empathy, intellectual perseverance, intellectual confidence in reason, intellectual sense of judgement etc. In the absence of these even the 'best' students leave college as 'mis' – educated persons.

Superficially absorbed content and shallow coverage of loads and loads of concepts leads to intellectual arrogance, whereas integrating teaching with critical thinking, moral integrity and citizenship is essential whereby persons become fair-minded and rational.

Some of the intellectual virtues which are worth mentioning are need to be discussed here :

* **Intellectual humility** : This makes a person conscious of the limitations of one's knowledge and viewpoints. One should not claim to know more than he knows. Example of ancient Greek insight is worth quoting here. Socrates was the wisest of the Greeks because only he knew how little he really understood.

Thus the books should focus not on passive reception of small parts of a large number of subjects but concrete and foundational ideas for developing of intellectual skills, abilities, concepts and virtues.

* **Intellectual courage** – Students should be encouraged to develop the vision so as to recognize absurd ideas and refuse to accept them, no matter how much accepted facts they might be.

* **Intellectual empathy** : There is a need to imagine oneself in the place of others and understand them and the circumstances for their action, so as to reach the truth. It also involves the willingness to admit one's mistakes.

* **Intellectual integrity:** This means the recognition of the need to be true to one's own thinking, and to practice what one preaches to others and to admit inconsistencies in one's own thought and action.

* **Intellectual perseverance:** This implies achieving insight such that one may pursue truth even in the face of adversities and opposition, even if it implies that you must stand alone.

* **Intellectually reasoning:** This means thinking logically and reasonably and training one's own rational faculties such that it leads to fulfillment of one's higher interests and welfare of humankind.

* The ultimate aim of education should be to develop these intellectual traits and character. Schools should not be just thought of a place of teaching and learning, but also a place where consciousness is aroused and illumined, where soul is purified and strengthened.

To conclude we can say that education without vision is a waste, education without values is crime and education without mission is a burden. The need for a sustainable human development and social growth is value based education, ethical education and need based education.

References

- Pathania, A.(2011) Teacher's role in quality enhancement and value education. Academe, Vol. XIV, No.1, Jan.
- Paul, R.(1993) Critical thinking : What Every Student Needs to Survive in a Ragidly Changing World. Pillon Beach, CA: Foundations for Critical Thinking. www.criticalthinking.org.
- www.2knowmyself.com
- www.studymode.com/essays/degradation-of-Moral-Values-In-Indian-190390.html.
- www.ajms.co.in/sites/sjms/index.php/ajms/article/view/574/494.

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